

**METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING PRACTICAL-PROCESS COMPETENCY OF
STUDENTS IN PHYSICS IN HIGHER MEDICAL EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS
BASED ON QUESTIONS WHICH PRODUCE CRITICAL AND EXPRESSIVE
THINKING**

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ABSTRACT

This article notes that the main place in the formation of practical-process competence of students is realized through questions asked to students as methodological methods, as well as analysis of the results of methodological work of the activities of all students. Methodological structures in the last academic year, the levels of knowledge and skills of teachers, and issues of their planning taking into account professional interests and requirements were also considered.

keywords: physics, practical competence, teaching process, skills and qualifications, student, independent work, technology, methodology, how, questions, why.

INTRODUCTION

Scientific competence is one of the main components of the practical-process competence of medical university students and reflects the presence of the necessary professional knowledge and skills. Professional knowledge, first of all, includes knowledge of the subject that the teacher teaches students: conducting observations and experiments, making measurements, processing and explaining the results of experimental work; mastering the basic concepts and laws of physics, understanding the physical meaning of concepts and quantities; knowledge of physical phenomena, laws and theories.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

In determining the essence of the concept of practical-process competence, we rely on the research of I.V. Sorokina[1]. Summarizing the opinions of various authors, he proposes to understand the student's practical-process competence as "the optimal combination of knowledge, skills, abilities and experiences of a student who understands science-related problems." Based on the analysis of scientific literature, the practical-process competence of students of medical higher education institutions is revealed through specific knowledge and skills.

The practical-process competence of students of medical higher educational institutions in solving physical problems can be expressed by the combination of the following knowledge and skills: knows how to solve problems(knows the types of physical problems in all sections of the curriculum, methods of solving different types of problems); knows how to organize solving physical problems, organizes training sessions on solving problems taking into account the age and individual characteristics of students, can organize students' cognitive, including independent, activity in solving problems by creating problem situations[2].

The development of practical-process competences of students of medical higher education institutions based on physics is carried out through the work of methodical formations organized on a voluntary basis. The activities of all methodical structures should be planned taking into account the analysis of the results of the methodical work of the previous academic year, the knowledge and skill levels of physics teachers, their professional interests and requirements.

Kh.I.Isaev stated [3] that the main place in the formation of practical-process competence of students based on the science of physics is occupied by questions asked to students as methodical methods. The questions should be clear and concise.

RESULTS

Students develop critical thinking only when they begin to deal with a specific problem. Therefore, an important problematic question related to a situation or event, which is considered the starting point of the learning process, is a question that means what kind of problem this event creates. A student thinks only when struggling with a specific problem and looking for his own way out of a difficult situation[4], [5].

Simple questions: questions to name, remember and repeat some facts. What?, When?, Where?, How?.

Clarify questions. Such questions usually begin with the following words: So, you mean ...?, If I understood correctly, then ...?, I may be wrong, but, in my opinion, you .. ?. The purpose of these questions is to give the student an opportunity to reflect on what they have just said. Sometimes they are asked to obtain information that is not known, but implied.

Explanation questions. They usually ask, Why? and aimed at establishing causal relationships. Why do leaves on trees turn yellow in autumn? If the answer to this question is known, it becomes simple from explanation. Consequently, these types of questions work when there is an element of independence in the answer.

Creative questions. It includes control of the order of questions, convention elements, controls. What will change ..., What if?. How do you think the plot will develop? Then in the story...?.

Assessment questions. These questions are aimed at clarifying the criteria for evaluating the identified events, events, and facts. Why is something good but something bad? What makes one lesson different from another? How do you react to the hero's actions? and others.

Practical questions. This type of questions is aimed at establishing the relationship between theory and practice. How can you apply...?. What can be done from ...?. Where can you observe in everyday life ...?. How would you be in the place of the hero of the story?

DISCUSSION

In the teaching process, there should be a unit of reproductive and productive questions depending on the age of the students and the material to be studied. Questions allow them to shape their thinking, and the questions they are asked can often be open-ended questions used to gain control of the group (Table 1).

Table 1

Open questions

Question types	Content
Hypothetical	If ... what would you do/think? They help students imagine one or another situation, strengthen the thinking process.

Thought provoking	How can we help solve this problem?
Supporting	That's interesting, what happened next? They allow students to share their personal experiences and views.
Comment	What do you think about ...?" Such questions are used to let students know that their ideas are important and interesting.
The inquirer	Why do you think so? This question, asked calmly, helps them to think more deeply about their thoughts and analyze their explanations.
Explainer	Am I right if I say that you think...? Summarizing what the student has said and checking for understanding encourages others to think about how they might react to the idea.
Consenting	Do most people agree that...? Such questions can be used to encourage discussion. Or at the end of the discussion.
Dual	Try to remember not to use it, like "X is right, right? Such questions reduce the student's activity.

One of the effective methods of organizing the educational process is training. Here you can find help, active participation, help with assignments. Depending on the training programs, the loading of communication methods, skills and competences will be acquired. It is important to involve students in creating an ability to work with various sources, developing and developing their innovative resources, developing annotations to literature and articles on topics, and working with them on group assignments. These serve to guide the professional skills and qualifications of students in the process of methodical production

In pedagogy, the system of questions and answers of students is called conversation. The interview method, with the help of well-thought-out questions, takes into account the relationship between the teacher and the student, and leads to their independent thinking and acquisition of new concepts. In its application, the methods of asking questions, discussing students' answers, and forming conclusions are used. During the interview, the teacher pays special attention to the students' speech literacy. This is done with various explanations and their acceptance is clarified.

As the students get older, the problem questions they are asked also get bigger. When a problem situation arises, the connection between the fact and the result does not open suddenly, but gradually. This begs the question: What is it? (for example, we drop different objects into water: one sinks, the other does not sink); after describing some parts of the material, the student must guess (for example, melting ice, experimenting with hot water, solving a problem); the use of words such as sometimes, some, only in some cases serve as specific signs of knowledge; in order to understand a fact, it is necessary to compare it with other facts, perform some mental operations (for example, make different measurements, count with a group).

The method of free thinking is devoted to illustrative pictures, photographs and their discussion. The purpose of this activity is to expand the scope of knowledge and worldview of students, to gain knowledge and interest by introducing them to pictures, photos, and books, to acquire new knowledge by applying previously acquired knowledge, skills, and abilities in new situations. is to achieve their acquisitions. The announcement of a new topic can be organized in the form of heuristic conversation based on independent conclusions, studying the material, which shows the independence of students in understanding and mastering the material.

CONCLUSION

In short, questions activate students' perception, memory, thinking, speech, as well as develop critical and expressive thinking, help develop independent problem solving skills. The teacher of physics should use more complex questions, which are aimed at clarifying specific signs, properties, and results of practical actions, connections, relations, connections, and their explanation, in the formation of learning-cognitive competencies in students. More often such questions are asked by the physics teacher after demonstrating the sample or after the student completes the assignment. For example, they are asked when they divide a paper rectangle into two equal parts. what did you do? What is this part called? What is the shape of the part?

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